

Effect of Physical Infrastructures and Environment on Academic Achievement of Technical College Students in Nigeria

Dr Chuks Monday Nwabudike¹

Dr James Azuka Olisa²

Mrs Felicia Osakue³

¹School of Secondary Education (Technical)

²Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba

³School of Secondary Education (Technical)

Abstract

The study focused on the effectiveness of physical infrastructure and environment on the academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria. Four research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study population consists of principals and teachers in technical colleges in Nigeria, numbering 38,180. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by six technical education experts and two measurement and evaluation lecturers. The test-retest method, aided by Cronbach Alpha, was used to determine the reliability of the instrument, which yielded a 0.74 index. Responses to the research questions were analyzed using the mean rating and standard deviation, while the t-test was employed to test the hypotheses. The findings revealed, among others, that the physical infrastructure and environment affect the academic achievement of technical college students to a great extent. Similarly, tests of hypotheses showed no significant difference between the responses of teachers and principals on the extent to which physical infrastructure and environment affect the academic achievement of technical college students. The study recommended, among other things, that adequate physical infrastructure and a healthy environment should be put in place for technical colleges in Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Oladeji (2022) submitted that the infrastructure and environment in most technical colleges are not conducive to learning. Environmental influence is a major factor in the development of students' study habits. These environmental factors that influence students' academic achievement, according to Oguche (2022), comprise the topographical environment and physical structures for learning, which encompass buildings, facilities, and other infrastructure within the school premises. Orlu (2021) submitted that the concept of environment refers to the surroundings of schools' physical infrastructure in a particular area. In line with the above, school infrastructure comprises both the physical component of the school environment as well as the policies and system for managing the day-to-day activities of the school. The physical aspect of school structure refers to the buildings in which lessons are delivered to students and all other peripheral facilities therein. These facilities include library facilities, laboratories, workshops, bathrooms, toilets, furniture, staffrooms, etc. Usman (2019) described school structure from the perspective of policies and systems for managing schools and emphasized that it entails, among others, school curriculum and principals' leadership styles.

Students. Academic achievement represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which students have accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in the structural environment. It is also seen as students' success in meeting short- and long-term goals in education. Additionally, academic performance refers to the level of performance or accomplishment in schools. It is the core of educational growth. Academic achievement also means what the students have achieved at the end of the learning process based on the students' efforts.

Technical education is vital for development in every country of the world and Nigeria is not an exemption. A strong and effective educational system supported with good infrastructure and environment can boost the GDP of any country. Lack of resource materials, poor school climate or environment, inadequate facilities, type of learning environment etc. have tremendous impact on students' academic achievement. Consequently, improving students' academic achievement has long been an extremely complicated and vexing problem for education policy makers. Poor performance of students in technical colleges may be a reflection of the type of learning environment. Poor school environment may have negative influence on students' academic achievement especially if such environment lacks infrastructural materials, physical facilities etc. Schools' facilities are a potent factor to quantitative education. The importance of provision of adequate instructional facilities in schools cannot be overemphasized. Learning occurs through one's interaction with the environment. Environment here refers to facilities that are available to facilitate students' learning outcomes. It includes books, audio-visuals, software and hardware, instruments and materials for practicals etc.

Most researcher on students' academic achievement focused on either school curriculum, classroom environment, size of classroom, sitting position and arrangement, availability of tables, chairs, chalkboard. However, other factors including school learning environment, available infrastructure etc may affect learning outcomes. Some notable factors that may influence students' academic performance includes, school climate, instructional materials, physical facilities etc. This is because schools with a good and conducive environment that has the best instructional materials and physical facilities will produce better graduates with high achievement. Most at times, these facilities are not satisfactorily available or provided in schools. Favourable learning environment apparently enhances

significantly students' academic achievement. School environment enriched with modern facilities and good physical structures make students feel comfortable in their studies that results to high academic performance.

School environment is the immediate surroundings of the school which include classrooms, examination halls, workshops etc. Aliave (2022) stated that learning environment should have good infrastructural development such as physical facilities, electricity, well-stocked library, playground, laboratories, workshops, classroom etc. All these characteristics have positive impact on academic achievement of students in technical colleges.

Students require a school system/structure that is effective and a comfortable environment conducive for learning because there is a general perception of falling standard of education that in turn results in increased poor academic performance is due to poor learning environment and other important physical infrastructure. It is on this note that the researchers are prompted to study the effects of physical infrastructure and learning environment on academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria.

Problem Statement/Justifications

Educational facilities are grossly inadequate especially in public schools. These facilities constitute the most part of school learning environment. Besides the inadequacy, the available facilities are poorly utilized in some schools. These have multiplier effect on the ultimate academic achievement of learners. From dilapidated physical structures to poorly equipped libraries and laboratories. Inadequate infrastructure and poor learning environment makes learning very abstract and difficult for learners. Learning becomes herculean task when relevant educational facilities are not available. The state of physical structures and environment in some

technical colleges are not conducive for teaching and learning. All of the above components, of the environment have direct or indirect link to academic achievement. For instance, the cases of underutilization of available facilities abound in technical colleges. The focus of this study is to determine how physical infrastructure and learning environment affects academic achievement of technical college students.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to find out the effects of physical infrastructure and learning environment on academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria. The specific purpose is to find out;

1. How physical infrastructure and environment affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria
2. How physical building and premises affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria
3. How school location affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria
4. How administrative system affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. How does physical infrastructure and environment affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria?
2. How does physical building and premises affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria?
3. How does school location affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria?
4. How does administrative system affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

Ho₁: There is no significance difference in the mean responses of technical college principals and teachers regarding how school facilities affect academic performance of students in technical colleges

Ho₂: There is no significant mean difference in the responses of teachers and principals on how school physical building and premises affect academic performance of students in technical colleges.

METHODOLOGY

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The design of this study was a descriptive survey. It provides the opinion of the respondents on the effect of physical infrastructure and environment on the academic achievement of technical college students. Nwogu (2018) defines descriptive survey design as a study that aims at collecting data and describes, in a systematic way, the features of a given population. However, this design is considered appropriate because it enables the researcher to identify the characteristics of the population objectively. The population for this study consists of all the teachers and principals in all technical colleges in Nigeria. There are 457 technical colleges in Nigeria, with a teacher population of 30567 and a principal's population of 7613 (Source: Federal Ministry of Education, 2022). Therefore, the population of the study will be 38,180. Owing to the huge population size, Taro Yamane sampling techniques will be used to determine the exact number of respondents to be used for the study. The sample size of the study was 23648. Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. Primary sources of data were original data collected basically for the purpose of the study. In collecting primary data for the work, responses were elicited from the teachers and principals in technical colleges. These are data mainly sourced from already-made materials by other authors and researchers. They are available in relevant textbooks, journals, newspapers, and on the internet.

The instrument for data collection was a checklist and a questionnaire titled “Effect of Physical infrastructure and Environment on Academic Achievements of technical college Students Questionnaire”. The instrument was face and content-validated by experts. These experts were given the initial copies of the questionnaire as well as the purpose, research questions and hypotheses to critically examine the adequacy of the items and the weighing of the responses. These comments, suggestions and criticisms made independently by the experts helped the researcher to modify and

produce the final draft of the instrument. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, test-retest method was applied. The researcher with the help of three research assistants (whom are known to the researcher and understand the subject matter) administered the instrument directly to the respondents. A letter of introduction was attached to each of the instruments explaining the rationale for the study and an assurance of confidentiality regarding all information supplied for the study. The data was analyzed in tables using simple percentage (for research question one) and mean wherein nominal value was assigned to scaling items as follows (for questions two and three):

Strongly Agree = 4

Agree = 3

Disagree = 2

Strongly Agree = 1

The cutoff point was determined by finding the mean of nominal value assigned to the options. To achieve this, the normal values were summed up and divided by the number of rate. The formula used was;

$$x = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where mean

\sum = sum of

f = frequency

x = Score

N = Total number of scores.

That is,

$$\frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.50$$

Decision Rule

Any item that has mean of 2.50 and above was regarded as strongly agreed while mean scores below 2.50 was regarded as strongly disagreed. ANOVA was used for testing the hypotheses and where critical value is less than calculated value, the hypothesis was rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: How does physical infrastructure and environment affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria

Table 1: Responses on how physical infrastructure and environment affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria

S/N	physical infrastructure and environment affect academic achievement in the following ways	Teachers n=72		Decision	Principals n=302		Decision
		X	SD		X	SD	
1	Provision of well-equipped laboratory with adequate apparatus encourage class attendance	2.98	0.60	Great Extent	3.05	0.90	Great Extent
2	A positive, supportive and conscious classroom ambience Encourage active student engagement	3.00	0.82	Great Extent	3.00	0.76	Great Extent
3	Clinic or access to first aid kits in school affect student health and in turn their performance	2.96	0.85	Great Extent	3.01	0.76	Great Extent
4	Provision of instructional materials(aids) heighten students interests and ultimately affect their performance	3.22	0.59	Great Extent	3.04	0.33	Great Extent
5	Well-equipped library improves student engagement and examination preparedness	3.02	0.88	Great Extent	3.07	0.65	Great Extent
Grand Mean		3.04	0.73	Great Extent	3.03	0.69	Great Extent

Table 1 revealed that all listed items have mean scores above the cutoff point of 2.50 for teachers and principals alike. This implies that physical infrastructure and environment affect students' academic achievement.

Research Question 2 How does physical building and premises affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria

Table 2: Responses on how physical building and premises affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria

S/N	School physical building and premises affect academic achievement in the following ways:	Teachers n=72		Decision	Principals n=302		Decision
		X	SD		X	SD	
6	Offices and common-room for teachers aids their preparation of lesson note and in turn improves lesson acquired by students	2.74	0.95	Great Extent	2.81	0.90	Great Extent
7	Free rooms for reading help students engage in extra-moral reading for better examination performance	3.02	0.88	Great Extent	2.97	0.76	Great Extent
8	Dining hall gives students good lunch experience, which affect their respectability and retention of lessons afterwards	3.00	0.76	Great Extent	2.76	0.76	Great Extent
9	Adequate classroom spaces for teaching aid better student attendance	3.01	0.92	Great Extent	2.99	0.83	Great Extent
10	Indoor spaces and field for sports improves student engagement in physical and health education	2.89	0.88	Great Extent	2.82	0.94	Great Extent
11	Well painted and roofed building with electricity boost student attendance and academic engagement within school premises	2.96	0.60	Great Extent	3.01	0.65	Great Extent
Grand Mean		2.94	0.83	Great Extent	2.89	0.81	Great Extent

From table 2, all items, had mean (x) scores above the cutoff point of 2.50. Precisely, the implication of this is that these items that connected with school building and premises and they affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria

Research Question 3: How does school location affect academic achievement of technical college students in Nigeria?

Table 3: Responses on how school location affect technical college students' academic achievement in Nigeria

S/N	School location has the following effect on academic performance of students:	Teachers n=72		Decision	Principals n=302		Decision
		X	SD		X	SD	
12	Schools cited in remote areas affect academic performance	2.33	0.54	Little Extent	2.01	0.45	Little Extent
13	Schools in rural communities often lack adequate teachers which in turn affect student performance	3.00	0.88	Great Extent	2.97	0.76	Great Extent
14	Schools in rural communities lack adequate facilities, which affect student engagement in academics	2.98	0.95	Great Extent	2.81	0.90	Great Extent
15	School cited in noisy environment like market discourages students performance	2.96	0.76	Great Extent	2.76	0.76	Great Extent
16	Hoodlums often infiltrate schools cited in unsafe neighbourhood and negatively influence students' academic behaviour	3.22	0.62	Great Extent	2.93	0.33	Great Extent
17	Kidnapping, cultism and other forms of violence are prevalent in schools situated in unsecure location	3.02	0.82	Great Extent	2.96	0.75	Great Extent
Grand Mean		2.92	0.76	Great Extent	2.66	0.66	Great Extent

In table 3, all items, except 12, have mean (x) score above the 2.50 cut off point. This means that they were accepted to a great extent. The grand means from the respondents of teachers and principals also exceed the 2.50 cut off point, which implies that all the respondents posit that to a great extent, school location affect technical college students' academic achievement in Nigeria.

Research Question 4: How does school administrative system affect academic achievement academic of technical college students in Nigeria

Table 4: Responses on the extent administrative system affect technical college students in Nigeria

S/N	Administrative system affects academic performance in the following ways:	Teachers n=72		Decision	principals n=302		Decision
		X	SD		X	SD	
18	Regular payment and increment of teachers' basic salaries boost their job enthusiasm and in turn improves students learning process	2.96	0.82	Great Extent	2.76	0.90	Great Extent
19	Clinical supervision of teachers and students academic affairs by principals ensures that learning curricula are covered	3.22	0.85	Great Extent	2.81	0.76	Great Extent
20	Instituting and implementing good maintenance culture in schools increases the longevity of school facilities for improved academic engagement	2.74	0.60	Great Extent	2.97	0.76	Great Extent
21	Setting and enforcing simple rules of conduct in schools enhances effective students attendance, engagement and exam performance	3.02	0.59	Great Extent	3.44	0.33	Great Extent
22	Providing in-service training improves teacher classroom management skills, which improves students engagement and exam performance	2.91	0.83	Great Extent	3.01	1.01	Great Extent
23	Rewarding excellence and punishing misconduct encourage high teachers attendance and students learning rates	2.74	0.88	Great Extent	2.96	0.75	Great Extent
Grand Mean		2.93	0.76	Great Extent	2.99	0.75	Great Extent

Result from table 4, shows that all items were accepted to a great extent by both students and principals. The grand mean further affirm these findings as the mean cut off points of 2.50 were exceeded, which broadly implies that administrative system affect academic achievement technical college students in Nigeria

Test of Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significance difference in the mean responses of technical college principals and teachers regarding how school facilities affect academic performance of students in technical colleges

Table 5: t-test comparison of the mean ratings of teachers and principals on how school facilities affect academic performance of students in technical colleges

Group	N	X	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit
Teachers	22900	3.04	.73	372	-0.103	1.96
Principals	748	3.03	.69			

The analysis in Table 5 shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of t-cal is -0.103 which is not greater than 1.96 or less than -1.96, the null hypothesis is accepted as postulated.

Ho₂: There is no significant mean difference in the responses of teachers and principals on how school physical building and premises affect academic performance of students in technical colleges.

Table 6: t-test comparison of the mean ratings of teachers and principals on how school physical building and premises affect academic performance of students in technical colleges.

Group	N	X	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit
Teachers	22900	2.94	.83	372	-0.106	1.96
Students	748	2.89	.81			

The analysis in Table 6 shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of -0.106 which is not greater than 1.96 or less than -1.96, the null hypothesis is accepted meaning that there is no significant mean difference in the responses of teachers and principals on how school physical building and premises affect academic performance of students in technical colleges.

Summary of the Findings

1. Provision of well-equipped laboratory with adequate apparatus encourage class attendance; a positive, supportive and conscious classroom ambience encourage active student engagement; clinic or access to first aid kits in school affect student health and in turn their performance; provision of instructional materials(aids) heighten students interests and ultimately affect their performance and that well equipped library improves student engagement and examination preparedness.
2. Common-room for teachers aid their preparation of lesson note and in tum improves lesson acquired by students; free rooms for reading help students engage in extra-moral reading for better examination performance; dining hall gives students good lunch experience, which affect their receptability and retention of lessons afterwards; adequate classroom spaces for teaching aid better student attendance; indoor spaces and field for sports improves student engagement in physical and health education, and that well painted and roofed building with electricity boost student attendance and academic engagement within school premises to a great extent.
3. Schools in rural communities often lack adequate teachers which in turn affect student performance; schools in rural communities lack adequate facilities, which affect student engagement in academics; school cited in noisy

environment like market discourages students' performance; hoodlums often infiltrate schools cited in unsafe neighbourhood and negatively influence students' academic behaviour; kidnapping, cultism and other forms of violence are prevalent in schools situated in unsecure location

4. Regular payment and increment of teachers' basic salaries boost their job enthusiasm and in turn improves students learning process; clinical supervision of teachers and students academic affairs by principals ensures that learning curricula are covered; instituting and implementing good maintenance culture in schools increases the longevity of school facilities for improved academic engagement; setting and enforcing simple rules of conduct in schools enhances effective students attendance, engagement and exam performance; providing in-service training improves teacher classroom which improves students engagement and exam performance; management skills, rewarding excellence and punishing misconduct encourage high teachers attendance and students learning rates
5. There is no significant mean difference in the responses of teachers and principals on how school physical building and premises affect academic performance in students in technical colleges.
6. There is no significant mean difference in the responses of teachers and principals on how school location affect academic performance of students in technical colleges.

Conclusion

Effectiveness of physical infrastructure and environment on academic achievement of technical College students in Nigeria cannot be undermined. It was established that structural/environmental factors like school facilities, building & premises, local and administration in schools have great effect on student academic performance.

Recommendations

Sequel to the findings, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. Appropriate school authorities should endeavour to provide a conducive school environment that has good climate for effective teaching and learning. Such environment should be safe, students treated fairly by teachers and happy to be in school as well as feel they are a part of the school.
2. Government should provide adequate school physical facilities in technical colleges to enhance teaching and learning processes. The Parent Teacher Association (PTA), philanthropist and other charitable organizations are also implored to compliment the efforts of the government.
3. There is need to imbibe a good maintenance culture to help preserve existing school facilities, libraries and other school structures that influences students' performance. This way, these facilities will be durable to aid more students towards better academic performance.
4. Security measures should be put in place for schools situated in notorious ghetto and other unsafe environments hunted by bandits, kidnappers, touts/gangs and other hoodlums. This is to prevent students from learning these negative traits or even merely affected by the activities of these hoodlums.

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